

Customizing Classrooms: How Teachers Can Adapt Education to Fit Student Needs

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Abstract

Education is a fundamental driver of individual and societal development, yet traditional teaching methods often struggle to address the diverse needs of students in today's classrooms. In Mwanza City, Tanzania, this challenge is particularly pronounced, as educators face overcrowded classrooms, limited resources, and varying levels of student preparedness. This study explored the implementation of classroom customization in Mwanza City, examining how teachers adapt their teaching strategies to meet the diverse needs of students and the impact of these adaptations on student outcomes. The study focused on three key indicators: the frequency of customized teaching strategies used by teachers, the types of instructional methods and tools employed, and the preparedness of teachers for classroom customization. In addition, it assessed the impact of customization on student engagement, teaching flexibility, and academic performance. The study also identified challenges, including the availability of resources, teachers' and students' digital literacy levels, and institutional support for customization practices. Data was collected from 233 respondents, including teachers and education officials, using surveys and interviews. The findings revealed that while many teachers implemented customized strategies, challenges such as inadequate resources and limited institutional support hindered the full potential of classroom customization. The study underscores the need for improved professional development for teachers, better access to teaching resources, and stronger institutional support to ensure the effective and sustainable adoption of classroom customization in Mwanza City.

Keywords: *Classroom Customization, Adaptive Learning, Teaching Strategies, Student Engagement, Instructional Tools, Teacher Preparedness, Professional Development, Teaching Resources, Digital Literacy, Personalized Learning.*

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Introduction

Education is a fundamental driver of individual and societal development, yet traditional teaching methods often struggle to address the diverse needs of students in today's classrooms. In Mwanza City, Tanzania, this challenge is particularly pronounced, as educators face overcrowded classrooms, limited resources, and varying levels of student preparedness. The one-size-fits-all approach to education has proven inadequate in meeting the unique learning styles, paces, and interests of students, leading to disparities in academic performance and engagement. In response, there is a growing recognition of the need to customize classrooms and adapt teaching methods to better fit the needs of individual learners. This approach, often referred to as personalized or student-centered learning, emphasizes tailoring instruction to accommodate diverse learning preferences, abilities, and backgrounds.

The increasing diversity in schools presents significant challenges for educators, including overcrowded classrooms, limited resources, and varying student preparedness (Mao & Sun, 2023). Teachers face difficulties in classroom management, differentiation, and addressing language barriers and diverse learning styles (Sharma, 2023). The lack of language proficiency and culturally responsive teaching training creates barriers to effective schooling (Aydin, 2023). These challenges are particularly pronounced for students from culturally and linguistically diverse (CLD) backgrounds, who often experience underachievement and higher dropout rates (Chu, 2011). Factors contributing to this include racial gaps, social class, and cultural-ecological factors associated with involuntary minority status (Chu, 2011). To address these issues, researchers suggest targeted investments in under-resourced schools, teacher recruitment and retention, promotion of integration, and support for families (Mao & Sun, 2023). Additionally, implementing culturally responsive teaching practices is crucial for facilitating CLD students' learning and creating more equitable educational environments (Aydin, 2023; Chu, 2011).

Tanzania faces significant challenges in providing quality education to its diverse student population. Despite increased funding, schools struggle with overcrowded classrooms, limited resources, and varying levels of student preparedness (Tshabangu & Msafiri, 2013). Factors hindering quality education include inadequate teacher-student ratios, poor textbook quality, and lack of laboratory facilities (King, 2013). Weak management and insufficient funding of community secondary schools contribute to irregular student attendance and unauthorized cost-sharing, affecting access for economically disadvantaged families (Mtavangu, 2010). Additionally, political interference and lack of legal literacy among education managers impact teacher retention and gender equity in education (Mtavangu, 2010). Many children are excluded from education due to poverty, inequity, and discrimination based on factors such as gender, disability, and ethnicity (Stubbs, 2008). To address these issues, UNESCO supports the implementation of an Inclusive Education strategy, including piloting a toolkit to create inclusive and learner-friendly environments in Tanzanian schools (Stubbs, 2008).

Differentiated instruction is a framework that addresses student diversity in classrooms by providing varied learning approaches tailored to individual needs, abilities, and backgrounds (Tomlinson, 2017). This approach is particularly relevant in EFL contexts, where students come from diverse settings and possess unique individual differences (Tanjung & Ashadi, 2019). Culturally responsive pedagogy is crucial for supporting students from diverse cultural backgrounds, fostering inclusive environments where differences are celebrated (Richards et al., 2007). Effective

teaching strategies for diverse learners include collaborative learning environments, group interactions, and opportunities to demonstrate strengths in leadership and problem-solving (Gasman & Vultaggio, 2009). However, many faculty members lack the necessary training to create inclusive teaching environments that respond to different levels of academic skill and knowledge (Gasman & Vultaggio, 2009). By implementing differentiated instruction and culturally responsive practices, educators can better accommodate diverse learners and provide equal opportunities for all students to reach their full potential.

Research in Tanzania highlights the importance of customizing classrooms to address student diversity. Culturally-responsive instruction, including native language use and local materials, fosters inclusive learning environments and supports meaningful learning in early childhood education (Amani & Mgaiwa, 2025). However, challenges persist in higher education, where limited classroom support for digital literacy skills exists due to inadequate instructor preparation (Nalaila et al., 2022). In secondary schools, linguistic diversity creates communication barriers, necessitating strategies like bilingual instruction and visual aids (Nnko & Kalokola, 2023). Inclusive classrooms face challenges in teaching mixed-ability groups, particularly students with disabilities, though gender interactions are generally positive (Possi & Milinga, 2018). Recommendations include developing language support programs, investing in teacher training for managing diversity, and incorporating knowledge of learner diversity in initial and in-service teacher training to create equitable and inclusive learning environments (Nnko & Kalokola, 2023; Possi & Milinga, 2018).

Adaptive teaching is an instructional approach that recognizes and responds to individual student differences and needs (Corno, 2008; Vaughn et al., 2016). Effective adaptive teachers use their experience to diagnose student needs quickly, form flexible groups, and modify their practices on the fly (Corno, 2008). This approach requires both intellectual and technical skills, as teachers must read student signals and draw on previous experiences to respond productively (Corno, 2008; Parsons & Vaughn, 2013). Studies have identified characteristics of adaptive teachers and documented specific examples of adaptive practices in various subjects and grade levels (Gazioglu et al., 2022; Vaughn et al., 2016). Research highlights the complexity of classroom instruction and the importance of metacognitive processes in successful adaptive teaching (Parsons & Vaughn, 2013) (Parsons & Vaughn, 2014). While adaptive teaching offers benefits for student learning, beginning teachers may face challenges in implementing these strategies effectively (Gazioglu et al., 2022).

Recent research highlights the potential of personalized learning and AI to promote educational equity. Personalized approaches can address student heterogeneity and provide adequacy-based equity, though they may not achieve equality of outcomes (Dumont & Ready, 2023). AI technologies offer opportunities for enhancing accessibility, creating personalized experiences, and developing adaptive learning materials (Gabriel, 2024; Roshanaei et al., 2023). These tools can support students with disabilities, provide multilingual assistance, and offer immediate feedback, potentially breaking down traditional educational barriers (Gabriel, 2024). However, challenges persist, including digital divides and the risk of perpetuating biases (Gabriel, 2024). Inclusive education principles emphasize diversity, equity, and belonging for all students, including those with disabilities (Singh, 2024). To maximize the benefits of AI in education while promoting equity, a balanced approach combining human instruction with AI-supported learning is recommended (Gabriel, 2024; Roshanaei et al., 2023).

Research in Tanzania highlights challenges and opportunities for improving adaptive teaching strategies. Cultural context significantly influences classroom dynamics, necessitating adaptations to pedagogical practices while maintaining effective learning principles (Tibenda et al., 2021). In inclusive settings, teachers must employ diverse and flexible methods to address the unique needs of learners with disabilities, emphasizing curriculum modifications and differentiated instruction (Mrema, 2024). However, the effectiveness of teacher training, particularly teaching practice, has been questioned. A study found that the duration of teaching practice was inadequate, supervision was ineffective, and 76% of student teachers reported that it did not significantly improve their teaching skills (Komba & Kira, 2013). These findings underline the importance of culturally sensitive pedagogical adaptations, ongoing professional development for teachers in inclusive education strategies, and a review of teaching practice procedures to enhance teacher preparation and effectiveness in meeting diverse student needs.

Recent studies highlight the growing importance of student-centered approaches in education. While teachers generally hold positive attitudes towards these methods (Shewangizaw, 2024), there is often a gap between theory and practice, with many educators still relying on teacher-centered approaches (Alqahtani & Alhamami, 2024). Challenges include lack of practical skills, assessment constraints, and the need for continuous feedback (Shewangizaw, 2024). However, student-centered teaching can positively impact learning by stimulating interest and initiative. Students express a desire to participate in educational decision-making, particularly in assessment choices and curriculum design (Ograjšek & Grmek, 2024). To address these issues, teacher training programs should focus on developing practical skills for implementing student-centered approaches, and educational policies should create supportive environments for their adoption (Alqahtani & Alhamami, 2024; Shewangizaw, 2024).

Research in Tanzania has highlighted challenges in implementing learner-centered teaching (LCT) approaches in secondary schools. Studies have found that teachers often lack understanding and training in LCT methods, leading to continued use of traditional teacher-centered approaches (Mligo et al., 2016; Mtitu, 2014). Large class sizes, insufficient resources, and untrained teachers further hinder LCT implementation (Ishemo, 2021; Mligo et al., 2016). The effectiveness of student-centered approaches depends on factors such as student ability, learning environment, class size, teacher competence, and students' economic background (Malisa & Lyamuya, 2022). To improve LCT implementation, recommendations include providing initial teacher education and professional development, addressing resource shortages, and redesigning curricula to allow for more teacher flexibility (Mligo et al., 2016; Mtitu, 2014). Additionally, preparing students from the primary level for secondary education and considering the adequacy of teaching resources when implementing free education policies could support more effective LCT practices (Malisa & Lyamuya, 2022).

The problem of the study was that, despite the recognized importance of customizing classrooms to meet diverse student needs, many teachers in Mwanza City struggled to effectively implement adaptive teaching strategies due to several persistent challenges. While classrooms in Mwanza were characterized by students with varying academic abilities, cultural backgrounds, and learning preferences, teachers often relied on traditional, uniform teaching methods that did not fully address these differences. Factors such as overcrowded classrooms, insufficient teaching resources, limited access to professional development, and a lack of institutional support hindered

teachers' ability to fully personalize learning experiences. As a result, many students were at risk of disengagement and underachievement. The study aimed to investigate how teachers in Mwanza City had adapted their instructional practices to fit individual student needs, the challenges they encountered in doing so, and the extent to which these efforts had contributed to improved learning outcomes and engagement among students.

The main objective of the study was to examine how teachers in Mwanza City customized their classrooms to meet the diverse needs of students. Specifically, the study aimed to assess the different strategies teachers employed to adapt their teaching methods and learning environments, to evaluate the challenges teachers faced in implementing classroom customization, and to determine the perceived impact of these customized approaches on student engagement and academic performance.

The study contributed valuable insights into how teachers in Mwanza City addressed the diverse needs of their students through classroom customization. It provided an in-depth understanding of the adaptive strategies teachers used, such as differentiated instruction and the integration of various teaching tools, to create more inclusive and responsive learning environments. The study also highlighted the key challenges faced by educators, including limited resources, large class sizes, and insufficient professional development opportunities. Furthermore, it offered evidence of how these customized teaching practices positively influenced student engagement and academic performance, thus adding to the body of knowledge on inclusive education and providing practical information for policymakers, school administrators, and teachers seeking to enhance teaching effectiveness in diverse classroom settings.

Materials and Methods

The study employed a mixed-methods research design to comprehensively explore how teachers in Mwanza City customized their classrooms to meet diverse student needs. A total sample of 233 teachers from various public and private primary and secondary schools within Mwanza City was selected using a combination of purposive and stratified sampling techniques to ensure a representative range of experiences and teaching contexts.

Quantitative data was collected through structured questionnaires distributed to all 233 participants. The questionnaire contained both closed-ended and Likert-scale questions focusing on key aspects such as the frequency of classroom customization practices, the types of adaptive strategies used, the challenges encountered, and the perceived impact on student learning outcomes.

In addition, qualitative data was gathered through semi-structured interviews with a smaller sub-sample of teachers selected from the larger group. These interviews aimed to gain deeper insights into teachers' personal experiences, challenges, and perspectives regarding classroom customization efforts.

Quantitative data was analysed using descriptive statistics, including frequencies and percentages, while the qualitative data was subjected to thematic analysis to identify recurring themes and patterns. The mixed-methods approach allowed the study to combine broad statistical trends with rich, contextual narratives, providing a holistic understanding of classroom customization practices in Mwanza City.

Results

This section presented the findings and analysis of the study, which examined the impact of IT on modern education in Mwanza City, based on data collected from 200 respondents, including students, teachers, and education stakeholders. The results were analyzed through both quantitative and qualitative methods, providing insights into the extent of IT integration, the effectiveness of e-learning, and the challenges faced in adopting IT-driven learning solutions. The discussion explored how these findings aligned with existing research and their implications for improving digital learning environments in Mwanza's educational institutions.

Implementation of Classroom Customization in Mwanza City

The implementation of classroom customization in Mwanza City was evaluated through three key sub-indicators: the frequency of customized teaching strategies used by teachers, the types of instructional methods and tools employed to adapt to student needs, and teacher preparedness and professional development for classroom customization. These sub-indicators provided a comprehensive understanding of how effectively teachers integrated adaptive practices into their classrooms. The findings revealed insights into the extent to which customization was practiced, the variety of methods and tools utilized, and the level of training and support available to teachers, highlighting both successes and areas for improvement in the implementation process.

Frequency of customized teaching strategies used by teachers

The study as demonstrated in figure 1, revealed varying frequencies in the use of customized teaching strategies by teachers in Mwanza City, highlighting the different approaches and challenges faced by educators. A group of 78 teachers reported using customized teaching strategies frequently, often adapting their lessons to meet the individual needs of students. These teachers were proactive in employing differentiated instruction techniques, such as tailoring content to accommodate different learning styles and providing varied resources. One teacher explained:

"...I use customized strategies every day, whether it's through differentiated materials for students who need more support or allowing students to work in groups based on their strengths. I believe every student deserves a chance to learn in a way that suits them best..."

This approach to classroom customization was commonly observed among those with sufficient training and access to resources.

In contrast, 102 teachers indicated that they used customized strategies only occasionally. These teachers acknowledged the importance of adapting their teaching methods but faced challenges like overcrowded classrooms and limited time for lesson preparation. One respondent shared:

"...I try to customize my lessons when I can, but with so many students and little time to prepare, it's difficult to make it a daily practice. I focus more on group activities and sometimes adapt worksheets, but I can't do it for every lesson..."

This group of teachers demonstrated a desire to customize their teaching but were often limited by practical constraints.

Lastly, 53 teachers reported rarely using customized teaching strategies. These teachers cited barriers such as a lack of proper training, insufficient resources, and limited institutional support. One teacher expressed:

"...I would love to personalize my teaching more, but I haven't received enough training on how to do it effectively, and the resources are just not there. I stick to traditional methods because that's all I feel comfortable with..."

These responses highlighted how critical training and access to resources are in enabling teachers to implement customized strategies in their classrooms.

The varying frequencies of customized teaching strategies reflected the differences in teachers' readiness, available resources, and institutional support. While some teachers actively sought to personalize their lessons, others faced challenges that hindered consistent implementation.

Figure 1. Showing the Implementation of Classroom Customization

Types of instructional methods and tools employed to adapt to student needs

The study found that teachers in Mwanza City used a variety of instructional methods and tools to adapt their classrooms to meet the diverse needs of students. According to data in figure 1, a significant number of teachers, 85 respondents, reported that they frequently employed group work and peer learning strategies as part of their classroom customization efforts. These methods allowed students to collaborate, share ideas, and learn from one another, which teachers believed fostered a more inclusive and interactive learning environment. One teacher remarked:

"...I use group work and peer learning because it helps students who may be struggling to grasp certain concepts to learn from their peers. It also encourages more participation and helps build a sense of community in the classroom. When students work together, they learn not only from me but also from each other, which I think is more effective for some of them..."

This method was particularly favored because it allowed for differentiated instruction within the same classroom, meeting the needs of students with varying levels of understanding.

In addition to group work, 60 teachers reported utilizing ICT tools, such as projectors and tablets, to enhance their teaching practices and better engage students. The use of ICT enabled teachers to present lessons in a more dynamic and visually engaging

manner, which was especially beneficial for visual learners. Teachers with access to these tools were able to incorporate multimedia elements, such as videos, interactive presentations, and online resources, into their lessons. One respondent explained:

"...the use of tablets and projectors in my lessons has made a significant difference. It helps me present lessons more engagingly and ensures that students can access additional resources. For example, when we study a science topic, I can show them videos or simulations that they wouldn't otherwise experience in a textbook. This has really increased their interest in the subject matter..."

The use of technology in the classroom was seen as an effective way to meet the needs of students who may benefit from more interactive or visual learning experiences.

Furthermore, 88 teachers indicated that they regularly used differentiated materials, such as tailored worksheets, to cater to students' varying learning needs. These materials were designed to provide targeted support, offering more challenging tasks to advanced learners while giving additional guidance to students who required extra assistance. One teacher shared:

"...I try to differentiate my worksheets based on the students' abilities. Some students need simpler tasks, while others need more complex ones to keep them challenged. This allows me to ensure that all my students are engaged and learning at their own pace, without feeling overwhelmed or bored..."

This method was particularly useful in addressing the wide range of academic abilities in a single classroom and helped teachers personalize learning for each student.

The use of these instructional methods group work, ICT tools, and differentiated materials demonstrated a concerted effort by teachers in Mwanza City to provide a more personalized and effective learning experience for their students. These methods allowed for a diverse range of learning styles to be accommodated, ensuring that both advanced and struggling learners received the support they needed to succeed. However, challenges such as access to technology and the need for professional development in differentiating instruction were also acknowledged by several respondents.

Teacher preparedness and professional development for classroom customization

The study as in figure 1, revealed significant variation in teacher preparedness and professional development for classroom customization across Mwanza City. A group of 45 teachers reported being well-trained in classroom customization, indicating that they felt confident in adapting their teaching methods and materials to meet the diverse needs of students. These teachers had received extensive training in differentiation, inclusive education strategies, and the use of technology in the classroom. One teacher reflected:

"...I've had several workshops and training sessions that focused specifically on customizing my teaching. The training was comprehensive, and it gave me the skills I need to tailor my lessons. I feel confident when I need to adjust content for different learning needs, and I know how to use tools like projectors or interactive apps to support diverse learners..."

This group of teachers benefitted from continuous professional development programs, which equipped them with practical strategies and resources for customizing their classrooms effectively.

In contrast, 120 teachers reported having some training in classroom customization, suggesting that while they had received basic instruction on how to adjust their teaching methods, they often felt inadequately prepared for full implementation. These teachers acknowledged the importance of adapting their teaching but indicated that their training had not been comprehensive enough to fully address the challenges they faced in customizing their classrooms. One teacher shared:

"...I attended a few workshops on classroom customization, but they didn't go into enough depth. I know the basics, but when it comes to dealing with students with specific needs or using technology more effectively, I feel a bit unsure. More training would definitely help me feel more capable..."

This group of teachers often used a trial-and-error approach, attempting to implement strategies without feeling fully supported by formal training, which sometimes led to inconsistencies in their classroom customization efforts.

Lastly, 68 teachers reported that they were not trained in classroom customization, which significantly impacted their ability to effectively tailor their teaching methods to suit their students' needs. For these teachers, a lack of training meant that they primarily relied on traditional, one-size-fits-all teaching methods. One respondent expressed:

"...I've never received any formal training on how to customize my teaching for different student needs. I try my best to adjust my approach based on what I see in the classroom, but it's difficult without the proper tools or guidance. I feel like I could do so much more if I had the right training..."

This lack of professional development left many teachers struggling to meet the varied needs of their students, and they often felt overwhelmed by the demands of differentiating instruction without the necessary support or skills.

The disparity in teacher preparedness and professional development for classroom customization underscored the importance of providing adequate and comprehensive training for educators. While some teachers had the skills and confidence to customize their classrooms effectively, many others faced barriers due to insufficient training. The findings highlighted the need for more targeted and continuous professional development opportunities to support teachers in adapting their teaching strategies to meet the diverse needs of their students. Moreover, the challenges experienced by those who were not trained emphasized the crucial role that structured training programs play in enabling teachers to effectively implement classroom customization.

Impact of Classroom Customization on Student Outcomes

The impact of classroom customization on student outcomes was a key focus of the study, shedding light on how tailoring teaching methods affected various aspects of student engagement, teaching delivery, and academic performance. Teachers were asked about changes in student participation and engagement levels, perceived improvements in the flexibility of teaching, and the influence of customized learning on students' academic results. These sub-indicators provided valuable insights into the effectiveness of classroom customization, revealing both positive and challenging outcomes in adapting education to fit individual student needs. The following sections explore these findings in greater detail.

Figure 2. Showing the Impact of Classroom Customization on Student Outcomes

Changes in student engagement and classroom participation

The study revealed significant variations in student engagement and classroom participation following the implementation of classroom customization. According to the data in figure 2, a total of 140 teachers reported that there was an increase in student engagement and participation after adapting their teaching methods to better fit student needs. These teachers observed that students became more motivated and actively involved in their lessons, particularly when instruction was tailored to their interests and learning styles. One teacher noted:

"...since I started customizing my lessons, I've seen a noticeable improvement in how students engage. They seem more excited about the lessons because the material feels more relevant to them. For example, when I incorporate group work and projects that reflect their real-life experiences, they participate more willingly and take ownership of their learning..."

This group of teachers attributed the increase in student participation to the fact that students felt more included and catered to, with the classroom environment becoming more interactive and collaborative. The teachers highlighted that when students could relate to the material, they were more likely to engage actively, ask questions, and contribute to discussions.

In contrast, 63 teachers reported that there was no change in student engagement and participation levels. These teachers felt that while they made efforts to customize their lessons, student involvement remained the same as before. One respondent shared:

"...I've tried incorporating more student-centered activities and using different teaching materials, but it seems like my students still don't participate much. I think the issue might be deeper, like a lack of motivation or external factors that affect their interest in school. It hasn't really changed despite my efforts to adapt the teaching..."

This group of teachers acknowledged that while they had adopted some customized strategies, they were uncertain about the reasons behind the lack of noticeable change in student engagement. They often attributed the issue to factors outside the

classroom, such as student backgrounds or socio-economic challenges, which could influence their willingness or ability to participate actively in the classroom.

Lastly, 30 teachers reported that student engagement and participation had decreased since they started implementing classroom customization. These teachers expressed concern that, despite their best efforts to adapt their teaching, students seemed less engaged and less willing to participate. One teacher explained:

"...I honestly thought customizing my lessons would improve things, but instead, I've noticed a decline in student participation. Maybe it's because the lessons are too different from what they are used to, or perhaps the adjustments are overwhelming for some of them. I'm not sure, but it has been a challenge..."

This group of teachers found that certain students struggled with the changes, and in some cases, the new methods may have made them feel uncomfortable or disengaged. These teachers speculated that the shift towards more student-centered approaches, although beneficial for some, might have confused or alienated others who were more accustomed to traditional, teacher-directed learning.

The varying responses regarding changes in student engagement and participation highlighted the complex nature of classroom customization. While a significant portion of teachers observed an increase in student involvement, others faced challenges that hindered improvements. The findings suggested that the success of classroom customization in fostering student engagement may depend on factors such as the level of customization, the specific needs of the students, and the overall classroom environment. Teachers' ability to recognize and respond to the individual learning needs of their students played a crucial role in whether the changes led to positive or neutral outcomes in engagement.

Perceived improvement in teaching delivery and flexibility

The study revealed a significant positive perception regarding improvements in teaching delivery and flexibility following the implementation of classroom customization. As per figure 2, a total of 155 teachers reported that they perceived notable improvements in both the delivery of their lessons and their ability to be more flexible in responding to students' diverse learning needs. Teachers in this group highlighted how adapting their teaching methods and materials allowed them to create more dynamic and flexible learning environments. One teacher shared:

"...by customizing my teaching approach, I've been able to offer a more personalized experience for my students. The ability to adjust the pace and style of instruction based on each student's needs has made me more flexible and has definitely improved the quality of my teaching. I now feel more equipped to manage a diverse classroom and ensure that no student is left behind..."

These teachers emphasized how their newfound ability to customize lessons allowed them to better meet individual student needs, improving their confidence and effectiveness in delivering lessons.

In addition to greater flexibility, many teachers noted that classroom customization allowed them to experiment with various teaching methods, which enhanced their overall teaching experience. One teacher elaborated:

"...customizing my lessons has given me the freedom to try new strategies, like incorporating group discussions, multimedia tools, and interactive activities. This has made my teaching more engaging and has increased student participation. I feel like I'm not just lecturing anymore, but actively involving the students in the learning process, which has been very rewarding..."

The teachers in this group noted that the increased flexibility allowed them to adjust their approach as needed, whether that meant offering additional support for struggling students or extending the challenge for advanced learners. This level of adaptability was seen as one of the major benefits of classroom customization, as it helped to create a more inclusive and responsive teaching environment.

However, 78 teachers reported that they did not perceive an improvement in teaching delivery or flexibility following the implementation of classroom customization. For this group, despite efforts to adapt their teaching methods, they felt that the changes did not lead to significant improvements in how they delivered lessons or interacted with students. One teacher explained:

"...although I tried customizing my lessons to suit the different learning styles of my students, I haven't really seen much of a difference in the delivery. The materials I use are more varied now, but I don't feel that it has made me more flexible in how I teach. Some of the challenges, like maintaining student attention or managing time, still remain..."

These teachers acknowledged that while classroom customization was an interesting concept, it was difficult to implement effectively without additional support or training. They often found that their traditional teaching methods were still more efficient in certain contexts, and customizing lessons added complexity without necessarily yielding the expected improvements.

The disparity in responses highlights the varied experiences of teachers when adapting to classroom customization. While the majority of teachers perceived improvements in their teaching delivery and flexibility, a substantial group struggled to see tangible benefits. The findings suggest that the success of classroom customization in improving teaching practices depends on multiple factors, including the level of support provided to teachers, the resources available, and the individual teacher's readiness and ability to implement these changes effectively. For those who saw positive changes, classroom customization enabled a more dynamic and responsive teaching environment, but for others, the transition remained challenging and without significant impact.

Influence of classroom customization on students' academic performance

The study indicated that the influence of classroom customization on students' academic performance varied significantly across teachers' experiences. As per data in figure 2, 128 teachers reported that they had observed an improvement in their students' academic performance as a result of customizing their teaching strategies. These teachers attributed the enhanced performance to the more personalized and student-centered approach that they implemented. By adapting lessons to meet the diverse needs of students, they were able to provide targeted support and help students better understand the material. One teacher remarked:

"...I have seen significant improvements in my students' test scores and overall academic performance. By adjusting my teaching to their specific needs and learning styles, students who were once struggling began to catch up. For example, when I introduced more interactive activities and differentiated assignments, I noticed that even the students who were previously disengaged became more interested in the lessons and performed better..."

These teachers believed that the use of differentiated teaching methods, such as group work, peer discussions, and tailored assignments, allowed students to grasp concepts more effectively and retain information better.

Moreover, the customization of lessons allowed for the identification and addressing of individual learning gaps. One teacher shared:

"...the improvements were clear when I was able to spend more time with students who needed extra support, while also challenging the more advanced learners. Customization helped me find the right balance. Students who needed more time to understand concepts received it, and those who were excelling were given additional materials that pushed them further..."

According to this group, the targeted support that came from classroom customization played a critical role in the improved academic performance of students, fostering a more supportive and productive learning environment.

On the other hand, 70 teachers reported that there was no significant change in their students' academic performance after implementing classroom customization. These teachers felt that while the teaching methods became more adaptable and varied, the students' academic outcomes did not show the anticipated improvement. One teacher stated:

"...I made the effort to personalize my lessons and incorporated various teaching tools, but honestly, I haven't noticed much change in my students' grades or overall performance. I think some of the students might still be facing external challenges, and these factors are more influential than the changes in my teaching methods..."

For these teachers, the lack of significant change in academic performance was often attributed to factors beyond the classroom, such as socio-economic challenges, family issues, or student motivation, which were seen as barriers to improving academic results despite more personalized instruction.

Lastly, 35 teachers observed that students' academic performance had actually declined following the introduction of classroom customization. This group of teachers expressed concern that the new methods might have overwhelmed some students or disrupted their learning habits. One teacher explained:

"...while I thought classroom customization would help my students, I actually noticed a decline in their performance. Some students, especially those who struggle with changes, seemed confused by the new approach and couldn't keep up. I even had some students who became disengaged because they weren't used to the changes in the classroom. It felt like too much too soon, and it negatively impacted their grades..."

These teachers found that the shift towards more student-centered learning methods created challenges, particularly for students who were more comfortable with traditional, teacher-directed instruction. The changes in teaching style, although beneficial for some, led to confusion and frustration among others, ultimately impacting their academic performance.

The disparity in responses highlights the complex relationship between classroom customization and students' academic performance. While the majority of teachers saw improvements in student outcomes, a notable portion of teachers either observed no change or even a decline in performance. These findings suggest that while classroom customization can have a positive effect on student achievement, its success depends on factors such as the individual needs of the students, the extent to which the teaching methods align with students' learning styles, and the level of support provided to students during the transition to a more customized learning environment.

Challenges Faced in Customizing Classrooms

The study explored the challenges faced in customizing classrooms in Mwanza City, focusing on key factors that influenced the successful implementation of adaptive teaching strategies. These challenges were related to the availability and accessibility of teaching resources and infrastructure, the teachers' and students' skills in applying or benefiting from adaptive learning methods, and the institutional support and policy frameworks for classroom customization practices. The findings revealed that while some teachers experienced success in adapting their teaching methods, several obstacles hindered the full potential of classroom customization. Issues related to inadequate resources, varying levels of digital literacy, and limited institutional support were identified as significant barriers to effective implementation.

Figure 3. Showing the Challenges Faced in Customizing Classrooms

Availability and accessibility of teaching resources and infrastructure

The study as in figure 3, revealed significant challenges related to the availability and accessibility of teaching resources and infrastructure in customizing classrooms. While 58 teachers reported having adequate resources, the overwhelming majority, 175 teachers, indicated that the resources available to them were inadequate, hindering their ability to effectively implement classroom customization. Teachers who had access to sufficient resources noted that having the right tools played a critical role in adapting their teaching strategies. One teacher shared:

"...I have been fortunate to work in a school that provides me with modern teaching tools such as projectors, tablets, and internet access. These resources have allowed me to design more interactive and engaging lessons that cater to different learning styles. Without these tools, I believe my ability to customize lessons would be severely limited..."

These teachers emphasized that access to technology and diverse teaching materials made it easier to tailor lessons to individual student needs, enhancing the overall learning experience.

However, for the majority of teachers, the lack of resources was a major obstacle to successfully customizing their classrooms. 175 teachers reported facing challenges related to insufficient infrastructure, outdated technology, and limited access to educational materials. One teacher explained:

"...it has been very challenging to customize my lessons when the resources are not available. I don't have access to projectors, computers, or even a reliable internet connection. I have tried using printed handouts and some locally sourced materials, but it is not the same as having proper digital tools. My efforts to incorporate multimedia or interactive activities often fail due to these limitations..."

Many teachers in this group expressed frustration over the lack of basic infrastructure like functioning computers or internet connectivity, which made it difficult to implement more modern and interactive teaching methods.

Another teacher echoed this sentiment, saying:

"...the biggest challenge I face is the lack of consistent access to the internet. I often plan lessons that require online resources, but when the internet is down, I can't deliver those lessons as intended. It feels like I'm always playing catch-up because I have to revert to traditional methods. Classroom customization requires up-to-date resources, but we simply don't have them..."

These responses highlight the significant gap in infrastructure that many teachers faced when attempting to adapt their teaching methods. Despite their best efforts to personalize learning, the lack of resources limited their ability to fully implement innovative strategies.

Moreover, some teachers mentioned that the scarcity of resources also created inequities between different schools. One teacher from a rural school stated:

"...in our school, we don't have the same access to resources as those in urban areas. While I try to be creative with the resources available, it's difficult to engage students with the same level of technology that other schools use. The lack of resources in my school is a huge barrier to customizing lessons to fit individual student needs. Some students miss out because I can't provide the same level of support as a teacher with better resources..."

This disparity was seen as a major challenge, with some teachers feeling disadvantaged in their attempts to provide an equitable learning environment.

These challenges reflect a broader issue within the education system, where disparities in resource allocation have hindered the ability of teachers to customize classrooms effectively. Despite the enthusiasm of teachers to embrace adaptive teaching methods, the insufficient infrastructure and limited resources were seen as insurmountable barriers for many, preventing them from fully capitalizing on the potential benefits of classroom customization. The lack of access to adequate resources was consistently cited as one of the greatest obstacles to implementing personalized, technology-driven, and engaging teaching practices.

Teachers' and students' skills in applying or benefiting from adaptive learning methods

The study revealed that the ability of both teachers and students to apply or benefit from adaptive learning methods varied significantly. As demonstrated in figure 3, among the respondents, 55 teachers reported that both their own skills and the skills of their students in applying adaptive learning methods were high, which contributed positively to their classroom customization efforts. These teachers felt confident in using various teaching strategies tailored to their students' needs, and their students demonstrated the ability to engage effectively with adaptive learning techniques. One teacher shared:

"...I have attended several workshops on adaptive learning, and I can confidently say that I understand how to personalize lessons for my students. The students themselves have become quite adept at using technology and participating in activities that support their learning styles. When I introduced more interactive elements into the lessons, they embraced it, and their performance improved. It feels like they are learning in a way that suits them best..."

This group of teachers emphasized that their proficiency with adaptive learning tools and methods, along with the students' ability to engage with them, made it easier to customize lessons to fit individual learning needs.

However, a larger portion of the teachers, 105 teachers, indicated that both they and their students had moderate skills in applying or benefiting from adaptive learning methods. These teachers acknowledged the importance of adapting teaching methods to suit diverse student needs but felt that both they and their students still had room for improvement. One teacher expressed:

"...while I've learned to modify my lessons to some extent, I still feel that I'm not fully utilizing adaptive learning strategies. My students are trying to engage with the content, but sometimes they struggle to navigate the learning tools we use. It's a bit of a challenge because not all students have the same level of digital literacy or the ability to self-direct their learning..."

This group of teachers highlighted that although they recognized the value of adaptive learning and attempted to implement it, they often faced challenges related to their own proficiency and the varying levels of digital literacy among their students. The teachers noted that many students struggled with the independent, self-paced aspects of adaptive learning and often required additional guidance to make the most of these strategies.

Furthermore, 73 teachers reported that both their own skills and the skills of their students in applying adaptive learning methods were low. This group of teachers expressed significant concerns about their ability to effectively implement adaptive learning strategies and noted that many students found it difficult to benefit from personalized approaches. One teacher explained:

"...I am still learning how to apply adaptive learning techniques in my classroom. I find it difficult to adjust lessons quickly enough to meet all the needs of my students, especially since some of them have trouble with technology. I also feel that many of my students are overwhelmed by the complexity of some of the tools we use. It's frustrating because I want to help them, but it feels like they're not ready for this kind of learning..."

This response reflects the challenges many teachers faced, as they struggled not only with their own limited knowledge of adaptive learning methods but also with the students' difficulties in adapting to new technologies and teaching strategies. For these

teachers, the lack of proficiency in applying adaptive learning methods made it challenging to personalize the learning experience in a meaningful way.

Additionally, some teachers from this group expressed concerns that the gap in digital literacy between themselves and their students further exacerbated the challenges. One teacher remarked:

"...the students who have better access to technology at home seem to do better with the adaptive learning tools, but those who don't have the same level of exposure are left behind. This uneven skill level creates a barrier to effective classroom customization. I try my best to make adjustments, but it's hard to create a one-size-fits-all solution when some students are struggling just to understand the basics of using the tools..."

These comments underline the difficulty in implementing adaptive learning methods when there is a significant disparity in the digital skills of students.

The differences in skill levels among teachers and students highlight a major barrier to the successful adoption of adaptive learning methods in the classroom. While some teachers were able to effectively implement customized learning experiences, many others faced significant challenges due to insufficient skills and experience. The lack of confidence and experience with adaptive learning methods, coupled with varying student abilities, made it difficult for many teachers to fully utilize the benefits of classroom customization. This finding emphasises the importance of continuous professional development for teachers and the need for improved digital literacy programs for students to ensure the success of adaptive learning initiatives.

Institutional support and policy frameworks for classroom customization practices

The study revealed varying levels of institutional support for classroom customization practices in Mwanza City, with teachers experiencing different levels of assistance from their schools and educational policies. As in figure 3, out of the respondents, 48 teachers reported receiving strong support from their institutions, which significantly contributed to the successful implementation of adaptive teaching strategies. These teachers felt that their schools provided the necessary resources, professional development, and encouragement to implement classroom customization effectively. One teacher shared:

"...our school administration has been incredibly supportive of classroom customization. We have access to regular training sessions, the latest teaching tools, and the resources we need to adjust our lessons to better suit student needs. The leadership is very open to new ideas, which has helped create a conducive environment for change. Without this strong support, I don't think I would have been able to implement adaptive learning strategies as effectively as I have..."

Teachers who received strong institutional support noted that it enabled them to focus more on improving their teaching practices, as they were provided with the necessary resources and professional growth opportunities.

In contrast, 95 teachers reported receiving moderate support from their institutions, which had a mixed impact on their ability to customize classrooms. While these teachers acknowledged some institutional backing, they felt that the support was often inconsistent or insufficient to meet the demands of adaptive learning. One teacher explained:

"...the school provides some support, but it's not always enough. Occasionally, we have workshops or access to materials, but these are not regular or comprehensive enough to make a

real difference. Sometimes, we are left to figure things out on our own, which can be frustrating. I wish there was more ongoing guidance and clearer policies to help us through the process of classroom customization..."

For these teachers, while there was some institutional support, it often lacked continuity and depth, which made it challenging to implement adaptive learning strategies consistently. These teachers expressed the need for more comprehensive policy frameworks that could guide them in effectively customizing their classrooms to meet diverse student needs.

On the other hand, 90 teachers reported receiving minimal or no support from their institutions in terms of policy frameworks or resources for classroom customization. These teachers faced significant barriers to implementing adaptive learning strategies due to a lack of institutional backing. One teacher from this group shared:

"...I don't receive much support from the school. We don't have any specific policies or guidelines about classroom customization, and the resources available to us are very limited. I feel that if the institution had more structured support or clear policies, it would be easier to make the necessary adjustments to my teaching. Right now, it feels like I'm working in isolation, and it's hard to sustain these efforts on my own..."

This lack of support led many teachers in this group to struggle with customizing their classrooms, as they had to navigate the challenges of adapting their teaching methods without the guidance or infrastructure that would have facilitated their efforts.

Another teacher from the group with minimal institutional support echoed similar sentiments, saying:

"...there is no clear policy on how to customize lessons for students with different needs. The administration doesn't seem to prioritize classroom customization, and as a result, we don't receive the training or resources that would help us implement it. I have tried to use my own methods, but without any institutional framework or policies to support me, it's difficult to make lasting changes in my classroom..."

The absence of clear policies and institutional support was a major challenge for these teachers, making it difficult to implement sustainable classroom customization practices.

The disparity in institutional support reflects a broader issue within the educational system in Mwanza City, where the degree of support for classroom customization is inconsistent. Teachers who received strong institutional backing were better equipped to customize their classrooms and improve teaching practices, while those with moderate or minimal support faced significant challenges. This discrepancy highlights the importance of establishing comprehensive institutional policies and frameworks that provide clear guidelines and consistent support for teachers seeking to implement adaptive learning strategies. The study suggests that a stronger commitment from educational institutions to support classroom customization through structured policies, ongoing professional development, and resource allocation is essential for achieving more widespread and effective implementation of personalized teaching methods.

Conclusion

The study provided valuable insights into the implementation of classroom customization in Mwanza City, highlighting various factors that influenced the adoption and effectiveness of adaptive learning methods. It was found that many

teachers employed customized teaching strategies, though the frequency and extent of their use varied across different schools. Teacher preparedness and the availability of resources played significant roles, with some teachers receiving strong institutional support, while others faced challenges due to insufficient resources or a lack of clear policy frameworks. The impact of classroom customization on student engagement was generally positive, with many teachers reporting increased participation and improved academic performance. Teachers also noted improvements in their teaching flexibility and delivery by adapting their methods to better suit the diverse needs of their students. However, several challenges, such as insufficient institutional support, limited access to teaching resources, and varying levels of digital literacy among teachers and students, hindered the full potential of classroom customization. These challenges highlighted the importance of structured policies and consistent support to facilitate the widespread implementation of adaptive learning strategies. The findings emphasized that a more robust commitment from educational institutions, including the provision of adequate resources and continuous professional development, is necessary to ensure the sustainable success of classroom customization in Mwanza City.

Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that educational institutions in Mwanza City prioritize the development of clear policies and frameworks to support classroom customization. This includes investing in the provision of adequate teaching resources, such as ICT tools and differentiated materials, to help teachers adapt their classrooms to meet diverse student needs. In addition, ongoing professional development and training should be provided to teachers, ensuring they are well-prepared to implement adaptive learning strategies effectively. Strengthening institutional support, including providing regular workshops, clear guidelines, and consistent follow-up, would further enhance the successful integration of customized teaching methods. Moreover, addressing the gaps in digital literacy among both teachers and students is crucial to ensure that all stakeholders can fully benefit from classroom customization initiatives.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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